

Transcriptomics Study of Patients with Pulmonary Fibrosis Identifies Disrupted Cilium Assemblies Associated with the Spread of Pulmonary Fibrosis

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Abstract

The etiology of idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF), a progressive and persistent illness that lowers lung parenchyma scarring and accelerates mortality, is unknown. The disease's pathophysiology is currently thought to include repeated micro-injuries to an alveolar epithelium that is genetically predisposed, followed by an abnormal reparative response that is marked by excessive collagen deposition. Therefore, identifying the fundamental causes of this illness may help develop a unique Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF) therapy strategy. To identify fundamental variations at the transcriptomics level between Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis samples and Healthy Control samples, a thorough analysis of the total RNA microarray processed data from GEO for IPF patients was conducted. Therefore, using the NCBI-Bio project (PRJNA432951) as a reference, we conducted a variety of bioinformatics studies on the transcriptional profiles of 33 samples in the current study, including 11 Control samples and 22 Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis samples. First, exploratory data analysis based on gene expression data using principal component analysis (PCA) depicted distinct patterns between IPF and control samples. There were 23,022 substantially differently expressed genes ($p_{\text{adj}} \text{ value} = \pm 1.5$) between these settings, according to the Welch's T-test differential gene expression study that followed. In lung diseases including cystic fibrosis, pulmonary fibrosis disease, and others, genes like CFAP43, DNAH11, CFAP206, and CCDC39 are identified in this study as critical characteristics that may significantly contribute to the loss of ciliary functions. Genes linked to ciliary dyskinesias in IPF patients are also suggested by this investigation. The findings reported here eventually provide fresh light on IPF and its relationship to lung disease prognosis.

Keywords: Pulmonary fibrosis, ciliary dyskinesia, Bioinformatics, Transcriptomics, Lung disorders

Introduction

Pulmonary fibrosis is a type of fibrosis where the irregular changes that result in fibrosis occur in the lungs. These changes in the lungs stem from the continuous injury of the alveoli, whether it be from infection, environmental exposure, or heredity [1]. Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis occurs when there is no apparent cause of pulmonary fibrosis, along with a sporadic and irreversible appearance of pulmonary fibrosis in the body. While there is not a cemented understanding of the developing mechanisms of the disease, it is thought to initiate through the chronic injuries of epithelial cells. The continuous wound-healing process that results from the injuries triggers the differentiation of fibroblasts into myofibroblasts [2]. These activated myofibroblasts express smooth muscle actin, which induces mechanical tension in the muscles and releases the extracellular matrix, which aids in the remodeling of tissue [2]. Under normal circumstances, the remodeling of the tissue would stop as soon as the healing is complete, but this does not apply to patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis. In those who are affected by pulmonary fibrosis, the myofibroblasts continue to express smooth muscle actin and create a build-up of the extracellular matrix. The combination of all of these factors builds up to develop pulmonary fibrosis. Cystic fibrosis, like pulmonary fibrosis, affects the normal function of the lungs. Cystic fibrosis is an autosomal recessive genetic disease, usually diagnosed during infancy, that decreases the longevity of life. Similarly, pulmonary fibrosis has also been shown to be hereditary, appearing to have an autosomal dominant inheritance pattern. While the symptoms of pulmonary fibrosis can sporadically develop throughout an individual's life, the symptoms of cystic fibrosis are present during an individual's infancy. The symptoms of cystic fibrosis may seem acute, but bronchiectasis is responsible for

most of the severity and mortality of cystic fibrosis cases [3]. Like cystic fibrosis, pulmonary fibrosis has a low estimated mean survival, which is 2-5 years from the time of the initial diagnosis [4]. The estimated mortality rates for pulmonary fibrosis are about 64.3 deaths per million in men and 58.4 deaths per million in women [5]. The main goal of our study was to identify the root cause at the transcriptomics level for pulmonary fibrosis. Our main concern was to find the biological pathways that are affected by the irregular changes that occur in the lungs of individuals who have pulmonary fibrosis. We wanted to find out at the transcriptional level which genes are mutated or adversely affected. While there have been treatments that have helped those with pulmonary fibrosis, discovering the specific genes that lead to bronchiectasis, the buildup of thick, sticky mucus secretions in various organ systems, and the acute symptoms of those with pulmonary fibrosis report, could be indispensable in finding future treatments. Thus, in this study, we investigated transcriptomic profiles of the DNA sequences of healthy control samples and the sequences of samples with pulmonary fibrosis to understand the biological pathways and genes that are affected by using various bioinformatics techniques. After identifying the strikingly unusual genes between the two groups, we inspected the biological, molecular, and cellular pathways that are affected in those with pulmonary fibrosis.

Methodology

Data Acquisition and Pre-Processing

For this study, we took processed microarray data from the NCBI GEO [GSE110147]. The dataset was contributed by Marco Mura et al. (2018) and published as a bio project with accession number PRJNA432951. Transcriptome data contains the microarray processed Array design category of the transcript cluster using the [HuGene – 1₀ – st] Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array [transcript (gene) version] platform. This dataset is shown in table 1.

Disease State Number of Samples	
Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis	22
Non-specific interstitial pneumonia	10
Mixed IPF-NSIP	5
Normal control (Healthy)	11

Figure 1: Disease State and Number of Samples

As shown in Table 1 above, there were four sample groups, however, we chose to work on Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF) samples and control samples. This left us with 33 patients, 11 in control, and 22 in Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis. The microarray processed data were quantile normalized signal data. The processed data had Illumina probe ids. We mapped probe IDs with the gene

symbols using the SOFT family files.

Exploratory Analysis

We conducted an Exploratory Analysis to understand the difference between IPF patients and healthy controls. Statistical data analysis was performed using the Principal component analysis module integrated into the Metabo-Analyst platform. PCA was performed in one independent condition: Control group Vs Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis. Pairwise Score Plots, 2D Scores Plot, and Synchronized 3D Plots were studied to determine the patterns.

Differential Gene Expression Analysis

Differential Gene Expression (DGE) analysis was conducted by contrasting IPF samples with the control samples. The differential gene expression (DGE) analysis was performed using Welch's T-test [6]. When two groups have unequal sample sizes and variances –a Welch's Test can be applied [7]. The Welch's Test uses a one-step approach for DGE analysis and combines several methods. The significant genes were identified with the threshold of (p.adj value <0.05, Fold change ($\geq \pm 1.5$)).

Assessment of Discriminatory Potential of Significant Genes

Next, to assess and visualize the potential of significant genes in distinguishing both the classes of samples PCA and H-Clustering were performed with the selected set of significant RNA genes only. H-clustering (Distance: Euclidean, Linkage: average) was performed to understand the discriminatory potential of significant genes in distinguishing the IPF and Control samples based on their gene expression. Heatmaps were drawn to visualize the gene expression patterns among different classes of samples. Heatmaps show which genes are upregulated and down-regulated. The ranges of colors of tiles in a heatmap are scaled in proportion to gene expression values.

Gene Enrichment Analysis

The gene enrichment analysis for Gene Ontology (GO) was performed to delineate the biological implication of the significant genes, significantly (p.adj value <0.05, Fold change ($\geq \pm 1.5$)) enriched KEGG pathways were identified using the Enrichr [8]. Notably, enriched pathways and GO terms were also identified using the Enrichr Platform for significant up-regulated and down-regulated genes. Further, the Enrichr was also used to identify the associated Gene Ontology terms and biological pathways with significant up-regulated and down-regulated genes.

Results

Exploratory Data Analysis

By using various in silico techniques to define the underlying gene signature and biological pathways, we analyzed transcriptomics data of Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF) and Control samples. The complete

workflow of our current study is represented below in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Methodology Workflow

In our study, we used principal component analysis (PCA) for our data analysis. PCA is an ordination technique that minimizes information loss and increases interpretability. Additionally, it simplifies complex data by reducing dimensionality and finding the most significant samples in the dataset. We performed PCA to understand the amount of variation between Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF) and Controls. Figure 3 shows the variation between IPF and controls. The PC1 is 74.6%, PC2 is 8.8%, and PC3 = 1.6%. Based on this exploratory analysis, there is an evident amount of variation between IPF and control samples.

Figure 3: PCA Analysis Variation

Downstream Analysis

From our PCA results, it can be seen that the variation between IPF and Control samples is close to the maximum. Because of this, we further carried out a comparative analysis between IPF and the healthy Control samples. Based on Figure 4, the healthy Control samples and the Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis samples are well separated, which means that there is significant variation between these two groups. Thus, in our downstream analysis, we performed differential gene expression analysis between IPF and healthy Control samples. After we observed the variation between these two groups, Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis, and healthy Control samples, we investigated the reason for this

difference and its impacts at the level of gene regulation.

Figure 4: Comparative Analysis

Figure 5: Comparative Analysis

Figure 6: PCA Analysis

Differential Gene Expression Analysis

In order to interpret the biological variations in a transcriptome's gene transcript abundance, differential Genes Expression (DGE) Analysis is used. Wherein, an amount of 2409 substantially different genes were evaluated between the Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF) and Control samples ($p.adj$ value < 0.5 , Fold change $\geq \pm 1.5$). Among them, 858 genes were found to be significantly upregulated ($p.adj$ value < 0.5 , Fold

change $\geq +1.5$) genes and 16,081 genes were found to be significantly downregulated (p.adj value <0.5 , Fold change ≤ 1.5) in IPF in comparison to Control samples.

Figure 7: Clustering and Heat Map revealed variations among Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis and Control samples.

In order to determine whether relevant genes can form distinct clusters in the samples of Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis and Controls based on their gene expression, hierarchical clustering was conducted. A machine learning technique for cluster analysis that aims to show clustering between genes. According to the clustering results, Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis and Control samples form distinct clusters, as illustrated in Figure 7. Wherein Figure 8 displays a heatmap of the significant genes' expression patterns in the Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis and Control samples.

Figure 8: Dendrogram of Results.

Pathways Involved

Pathway analysis and the gene ontology analysis were performed by using Enrichr for both up-regulated genes and the down-regulated genes. Now according to the analysis of GO molecular function of the pathway analysis for the up-regulated gene, we can observe that by sorting p-value rank, RNA binding is the most affected, and from observing the cluster gram, we see that the KCDN2, KCDN3, GRIA2, NTRK3, NTRK2 are genes causing this phenomenon for the RNA binding as shown in the chart below and for the down-regulated genes of the GO molecular function of pathway analysis, the histone deacetylase activity is seen at the top among the others in case of the down-regulated genes and the next top one

Figure 9: Heatmap of Results.

is the nuclear receptor binding.

Figure 10: Up-regulated Genes of the Pathway Analysis.

Again, from analyzing the *GO_{Biological}* function, we can observe that for the up-regulated genes, the cilium assembly is mostly the affected one and for the down-regulated genes of the *GO_{Biological}* function pathway, the collagen-activated tyrosine kinase receptor signaling pathway is mentionable for being affected. It is shown in the supplementary figure.

Figure 11: Down-regulated Genes of the Pathway Analysis.

For the *GO_{cellular}* component pathway, we can see that the mRNA cleavage and polyadenylation specificity factor complex is seen at the top among the others for the down-regulated gene, and in the case of the up-regulated gene, it is the nuclear lumen and for the KEGG pathway, the most affected one is the ribosome biogenesis in the eukaryotes for the up-regulated gene from the pathway analysis. The bar graph diagram is shown below for a clear visualization of the pathway.

Validation of the Results

We can see in the heat map (Figure 9) that the majority of idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis associated genes are

Figure 12: Volcano Plot.

actually up-regulated. Also, in the Principal component analysis plot, we can clearly see the distinct clusters of the control samples and pulmonary fibrosis-affected samples and from analyzing the cellular and molecular pathways, we now have a clear result for our hypothesis. Finally, we can say that our validation results confirm our hypothesis. Therefore, our research revealed significant differences in gene expression between idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis samples and Healthy Control samples.

Discussion and Conclusions

IPF has traditionally been thought of as an alveolar disease that spares the airways; however, recent micro-CT analyses have suggested that small airway changes are an early pathologic feature of IPF, identifying thickening of small airway walls along with significant loss of terminal bronchioles within regions of minimal fibrosis [9]. However, this calls for the identification of changes at the transcriptomics level which leads to such drastic changes. While there have been treatments that have helped those with pulmonary fibrosis, discovering the specific genes that lead to bronchiectasis, the buildup of thick, sticky mucus secretions in various organ systems, and the acute symptoms those with pulmonary fibrosis report, could be indispensable in finding future treatments [10]. In this study, we have attempted to reveal the close association of Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis with several affected pathways at the biological, cellular, molecular, and KEGG levels using RNA-Seq Analysis. To identify differences in gene expression between Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis samples and Healthy control samples, RNA-Seq analysis was performed on RNA-seq samples obtained from GEO.

Exploratory data analysis using PCA revealed that the samples of both categories form separate clusters, depicting the vast genetic differences between the Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis samples and Healthy control samples. This hints towards the theory that there is something that triggers the progression of Pulmonary Fibrosis diseases which leads to obstruction of small airways and bronchiolitis at the transcriptomics level.

Further studies on the same level would be able to divulge the

series of events that take place during this transformation.

Based on differential gene expression analysis using Welch's T-Test, we observed 858 genes were significantly (adjusted P-value <0.05, Fold change ($\geq \pm 1.5$) upregulated and 16,081 (adjusted P-value <0.05, Fold change ($\geq \pm 1.5$) genes were downregulated. Next, the PCA plot and dendrogram from Hierarchical clustering indicated their significance in distinguishing between Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis and Healthy control samples. A heat map generated from these genes showed that most of the genes were downregulated in IPF samples whereas some of them were up-regulated in Healthy samples, highlighting differential expression in both populations.

Gene ontology analysis performed using Enrichr based on significant gene sets showed obvious involvement of genes, specifically in lung pathway degeneration, via functional annotation and clustering. However, hits were obtained for genes associated with disturbed cilium assemblies' biological pathways, Ribosome biogenesis, Disturbed nuclear biolumen pathways, and RNA binding pathways. Further, pathway analysis demonstrated a better understanding of the involvement of the gene sets in the down-regulation of pathways which involved mainly histone deacetylase activity, mRNA cleavage pathways, and transcription by mRNA polymerase 2 pathways. This study shows that as per our Gene set enrichment analysis, the most affected pathway at the Biological processes level is the cilium assemblies pathway. The associated genes with this pathway are CFAP43, DNAH11, CFAP206, and CCDC39 [as per Enrichr] as the key features that may substantially contribute to loss of ciliary functions in lung disorders like Cystic Fibrosis, Pulmonary Fibrosis disease, and further on.

However, since our study was focused on samples of patients with multiple sclerosis, the involvement of certain genes that are also associated with HD is something of great importance. Studies have shown that the DNAH11 gene is majorly involved in ciliary dyskinesia and abrupt microtubular activity [11]. Similarly, diseases associated with CCDC39 include Ciliary Dyskinesia, and Primary Ciliary Dyskinesia [12]. Gene Ontology (GO) annotations related to this gene include nucleotide binding. Diseases associated with CFAP206 include Cone-Rod Dystrophy 7 and Primary Ciliary Dyskinesia. These results, portrayed here, show that the major involvement of up-regulated genes, especially those associated with disturbed Cilium assembly pathways, are involved in varied types of lung diseases such as Ciliary Dyskinesia and Primary Ciliary Dyskinesia. This leads us to the point that the obvious up-regulation of these genes in IPF samples could be the probable cause of the progression of pulmonary Fibrosis at the transcriptomics levels. The presence of ciliated cells bearing motile cilia, specialized cell surface projections comprising axonemes made of microtubules, and dynein arms, which generate ATP-driven movement, is a distinguishing feature of the human airway epithelium

[13]. The crucial process of mucociliary clearance, which clears the airways of pathogens and inhaled particles, is mediated in the airways by cilia working in tandem with airway mucus. Primary ciliary dyskinesia, an inherited condition that causes inadequate mucociliary clearance, recurrent chest infections, and progressive deterioration of lung architecture, is the classic pathology of respiratory cilia [14]. Several studies have also shown that the structure and function of the cilia are aberrant in many acquired lung disorders.

In this context, there may be slight variations in the genes regulating the shape and function of the airway cilia that contribute to the elevated risk of illness brought on by environmental stress, notably cigarette smoking. Last but not least, the majority of the information on anomalies of the airway cilia in acquired lung illnesses is descriptive and lacks a comprehensive understanding of the underlying mechanisms [15]. New classes of pharmacological treatments to reverse/prevent improper mucociliary clearance cannot be developed unless the defective biology responsible for mucociliary dysfunction is identified, according to the understanding of abnormal mucociliary clearance in various acquired lung disorders [16].

Conclusively, our study revealed significant differences in gene expression between Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis samples and Healthy Control samples. Importantly, we confirm and validate the significant upregulation and down-regulation of genes involved in disturbed cellular, molecular, and biological human pathways. This most likely reveals an important clue to the etiology of this fatal pulmonary disease.

Future Work

In the future, intensive research is required to assess the precise effect of Pulmonary fibrosis on genes like CFAP43, DNAH11, CFAP206, and CCDC39. More comprehensive research is needed to support these findings stated above. As part of a future study, it would be interesting to understand the changes in Pulmonary Fibrosis pathogenesis and its effects on histone deacetylase activity, mRNA cleavage pathways, and transcription by mRNA polymerase 2 pathways. Assessment of these types would help researchers in the future to combat therapeutic targets for the better treatment of Pulmonary fibrosis.

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